

The Proof of Two Conjectures Related to Pell's Equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 4$

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Abstract—Let $D \neq 1$ be a positive non-square integer. In this paper are given the proofs for two conjectures related to Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 4$, proposed by A. Tekcan.

Keywords— Pell's equation, solutions of Pell's equation.

I. INTRODUCTION

LET $D \neq 1$ be any positive non-square integer and N be any fixed integer. The equation

$$x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm N \quad (1)$$

is known as Pell's equation. It is named mistakenly after John Pell (1611-1685) who was a mathematician who in fact did not contribute for solving it (see [2]).

For $N=1$, the Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 1$ is known as classical Pell's Equation and it has infinitely many solutions (x_n, y_n) for $n \geq 1$. There are different methods for finding the first non-trivial solution (x_1, y_1) called the fundamental solution from which all others are easily computed (see [3], and [8]).

There are many papers in which are considered different types of Pell's equation (see [4], [5], [6], [7]).

In these notes we will be focused on paper [1] in which A. Tekcan considered the equations:

$$x^2 - Dy^2 = \pm 4 \quad (2)$$

and among other results he obtained the following:

Theorem 1.1. If (x_1, y_1) is the fundamental solution of the Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = 4$ then

$$x_n = \frac{x_1 x_{n-1} + Dy_1 y_{n-1}}{2}; y_n = \frac{y_1 x_{n-1} + x_1 y_{n-1}}{2} \quad (3)$$

for $n \geq 2$.

Theorem 1.2. If (x_1, y_1) is the fundamental solution of the Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = -4$ then:

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$$\begin{cases} x_{2n+1} = \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_{2n-1} + 2Dx_1y_1y_{2n-1}}{4} \\ y_{2n+1} = \frac{2x_1y_1x_{2n-1} + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_{2n-1}}{4} \end{cases}, \quad (4)$$

for $n \geq 1$.

Also the following conjectures were proposed:

Conjecture 1.3. If (x_1, y_1) is the fundamental solution of the Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = 4$ then (x_n, y_n) satisfy the following recurrence relations

$$\begin{cases} x_n = (x_1 - 1)(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) - x_{n-3} \\ y_n = (x_1 - 1)(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2}) - y_{n-3} \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

for $n \geq 4$.

Conjecture 1.4. If (x_1, y_1) is the fundamental solution of the Pell's equation $x^2 - Dy^2 = -4$ then (x_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}) satisfy the following recurrence relations

$$\begin{cases} x_{2n+1} = (x_1^2 + 1)(x_{2n-1} + x_{2n-3}) - x_{2n-5} \\ y_{2n+1} = (x_1^2 + 1)(y_{2n-1} + y_{2n-3}) - y_{2n-5} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

for $n \geq 3$.

II. MAIN RESULTS. PROOF OF CONJECTURES

We will prove above mentioned conjectures using the method of mathematical induction.

Proof of conjecture 1.3

First, we show that relations (5) are true for $n = 4$, so we have to show:

$$\begin{cases} x_4 = (x_1 - 1)(x_3 + x_2) - x_1 \\ y_4 = (x_1 - 1)(y_3 + y_2) - y_1 \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Using (3) we obtain the following:

$$\begin{cases} x_2 = \frac{x_1^2 + Dy_1^2}{2} = \frac{x_1^2 + x_1^2 - 4}{2} = x_1^2 - 2 \\ y_2 = x_1 y_1 \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

Then by (3) and (8) we get:

$$\begin{cases} x_3 = \frac{x_1x_2 + Dy_1y_2}{2} = \frac{x_1(x_1^2 - 2) + Dy_1^2x_1}{2} \\ = x_1(x_1^2 - 3) \\ y_3 = \frac{y_1x_2 + x_1y_2}{2} = \frac{y_1(x_1^2 - 2) + x_1^2y_1}{2} \\ = y_1(x_1^2 - 1) \end{cases} \quad (9)$$

Next by (3) and (9) we find x_4 and y_4 :

$$\begin{aligned} x_4 &= \frac{x_1x_3 + Dy_1y_3}{2} = \frac{x_1^2(x_1^2 - 3) + Dy_1^2(x_1^2 - 1)}{2} \\ &= \frac{x_1^2(x_1^2 - 3) + (x_1^2 - 4)(x_1^2 - 1)}{2} = x_1^4 - 4x_1^2 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_4 &= \frac{y_1x_3 + x_1y_3}{2} = \frac{y_1x_1(x_1^2 - 3) + x_1y_1(x_1^2 - 1)}{2} \\ &= x_1y_1(x_1^2 - 2). \end{aligned}$$

So we obtained:

$$\begin{cases} x_4 = x_1^4 - 4x_1^2 + 2 \\ y_4 = x_1y_1(x_1^2 - 2) \end{cases} \quad (10)$$

Now, replacing (8) and (9) in (7) one obtains:

$$\begin{aligned} x_4 &= (x_1 - 1)(x_1(x_1^2 - 3) + x_1^2 - 2) - x_1 \\ &= (x_1 - 1)(x_1^3 + x_1^2 - 3x_1 - 2) - x_1 = x_1^4 - 4x_1^2 + 2 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} y_4 &= (x_1 - 1)(y_1(x_1^2 - 1) + x_1y_1) - y_1 \\ &= y_1((x_1 - 1)(x_1^2 - 1 + x_1) - 1) = x_1y_1(x_1^2 - 2) \end{aligned}$$

which are the same formulas as in (10).

It means for $n = 4$, the recurrence relations (5) hold.

Next, we assume that (5) holds for n and we show that it holds for $n + 1$.

Indeed, by (3) and by hypothesis we have:

$$\begin{aligned} x_{n+1} &= \frac{x_1((x_1 - 1)(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) - x_{n-3})}{2} + \\ &\quad + \frac{Dy_1((x_1 - 1)(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2}) - y_{n-3})}{2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1) \left(\frac{x_1(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) + Dy_1(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2})}{2} \right) - \frac{x_1x_{n-3} + Dy_1y_{n-3}}{2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1) \left(\frac{x_1x_{n-1} + Dy_1y_{n-1}}{2} + \frac{x_1x_{n-2} + Dy_1y_{n-2}}{2} \right) - x_{n-2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1)(x_n + x_{n-1}) - x_{n-2}, \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} y_{n+1} &= \frac{y_1((x_1 - 1)(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) - x_{n-3})}{2} + \\ &\quad + \frac{x_1((x_1 - 1)(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2}) - y_{n-3})}{2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1) \left(\frac{y_1(x_{n-1} + x_{n-2}) + x_1(y_{n-1} + y_{n-2})}{2} \right) - \frac{y_1x_{n-3} + x_1y_{n-3}}{2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1) \left(\frac{y_1x_{n-1} + x_1y_{n-1}}{2} + \frac{y_1x_{n-2} + x_1y_{n-2}}{2} \right) - y_{n-2} \\ &= (x_1 - 1)(y_n + y_{n-1}) - y_{n-2}, \end{aligned}$$

completing the proof.

Proof of conjecture 1.4

First, we show that relations (6) are true for $n = 3$, so we show that:

$$\begin{cases} x_7 = (x_1^2 + 1)(x_5 + x_3) - x_1 \\ y_7 = (x_1^2 + 1)(y_5 + y_3) - y_1 \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

Using (4) we obtain the following:

$$x_3 = \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_1 + 2Dx_1y_1^2}{4} = \frac{x_1(x_1^2 + 3Dy_1^2)}{4}.$$

Since (x_1, y_1) is the fundamental solution of $x^2 - Dy^2 = -4$ then $x_1^2 + 3Dy_1^2 = 4(Dy_1^2 - 1)$ and since $Dy_1^2 = x_1^2 + 4$ we obtain $x_3 = x_1(x_1^2 + 3)$. Then by (4) we have

$$\begin{aligned} y_3 &= \frac{2x_1y_1x_1 + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_1}{4} = \frac{y_1(3x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)}{4} \\ &= \frac{y_1(3x_1^2 + x_1^2 + 4)}{4} = y_1(x_1^2 + 1). \end{aligned}$$

So we have:

$$\begin{cases} x_3 = x_1(x_1^2 + 3) \\ y_3 = y_1(x_1^2 + 1) \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Then, using (4) and (12) we obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} x_5 &= \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_1(x_1^2 + 3) + 2Dx_1y_1^2(x_1^2 + 1)}{4} \\ &= \frac{(2x_1^2 + 4)x_1(x_1^2 + 3) + 2x_1(x_1^2 + 4)(x_1^2 + 1)}{4} \\ &= \frac{x_1}{2}((x_1^2 + 2)(x_1^2 + 3) + (x_1^2 + 4)(x_1^2 + 1)) \\ &= x_1(x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) \end{aligned}$$

and

$$y_5 = \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_3 + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_3}{4}$$

$$= \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_1 (x_1^2 + 3) + 2(x_1^2 + 2)y_1 (x_1^2 + 1)}{4}$$

$$= \frac{y_1}{2} (x_1^2 (x_1^2 + 3) + (x_1^2 + 2)(x_1^2 + 1)) = y_1 (x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1).$$

So we have.

$$\begin{cases} x_5 = x_1 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) \\ y_5 = y_1 (x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1) \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

Finally using (13) we obtain formulas for x_7 and y_7 depending on the fundamental solution (x_1, y_1) .

$$x_7 = \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_5 + 2Dx_1 y_1 y_5}{4}$$

$$= \frac{2(x_1^2 + 2)x_1 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + 2x_1 Dy_1^2 (x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1)}{4}$$

$$= \frac{(x_1^2 + 2)x_1 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + x_1^2 (x_1^2 + 4)(x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1)}{2}$$

$$= \frac{x_1}{2} ((x_1^2 + 2)(x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + (x_1^2 + 4)(x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1))$$

$$= x_1 (x_1^6 + 7x_1^4 + 14x_1^2 + 7)$$

and

$$y_7 = \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_5 + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_5}{4}$$

$$= \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_1 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + 2(x_1^2 + 2)y_1 (x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1)}{4}$$

$$= \frac{y_1}{2} (x_1^2 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + (x_1^2 + 2)(x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1))$$

$$= y_1 (x_1^6 + 5x_1^4 + 6x_1^2 + 1).$$

So

$$\begin{cases} x_7 = x_1 (x_1^6 + 7x_1^4 + 14x_1^2 + 7) \\ y_7 = y_1 (x_1^6 + 5x_1^4 + 6x_1^2 + 1) \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Now replacing (12) and (13) in (11) we obtain:

$$x_7 = (x_1^2 + 1)(x_5 + x_3) - x_1$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1)(x_1 (x_1^4 + 5x_1^2 + 5) + x_1 (x_1^2 + 3)) - x_1$$

$$= x_1 ((x_1^2 + 1)(x_1^4 + 6x_1^2 + 8) - 1) = x_1 (x_1^6 + 7x_1^4 + 14x_1^2 + 7)$$

and

$$y_7 = (x_1^2 + 1)(y_5 + y_3) - y_1$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1)(y_1 (x_1^4 + 3x_1^2 + 1) + y_1 (x_1^2 + 1)) - y_1$$

$= y_1 ((x_1^2 + 1)(x_1^4 + 4x_1^2 + 2) - 1) = y_1 (x_1^6 + 5x_1^4 + 6x_1^2 + 1)$
which proves that for $n = 3$ the recurrence relations (6) are true.

Now we assume that (x_{2n+1}, y_{2n+1}) satisfies (6) and we prove that also (x_{2n+3}, y_{2n+3}) satisfies (6).

Indeed by (4) and hypothesis we obtain.

$$x_{2n+3} = \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)((x_1^2 + 1)(x_{2n-1} + x_{2n-3}) - x_{2n-5})}{4} +$$

$$+ \frac{2Dx_1 y_1 ((x_1^2 + 1)(y_{2n-1} + y_{2n-3}) - y_{2n-5})}{4}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1) \frac{((x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)(x_{2n-1} + x_{2n-3}) + 2Dx_1 y_1 (y_{2n-1} + y_{2n-3}))}{4} -$$

$$- \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_{2n-5} + 2Dx_1 y_1 y_{2n-5}}{4}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1) \left(\frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_{2n-1} + 2Dx_1 y_1 y_{2n-1}}{4} + \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)x_{2n-3} + 2Dx_1 y_1 y_{2n-3}}{4} \right) - x_{2n-3}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1)(x_{2n+1} + x_{2n-1}) - x_{2n-3}$$

and

$$y_{2n+3} = \frac{2x_1 y_1 ((x_1^2 + 1)(x_{2n-1} + x_{2n-3}) - x_{2n-5})}{4} +$$

$$+ \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)((x_1^2 + 1)(y_{2n-1} + y_{2n-3}) - y_{2n-5})}{4}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1) \left(\frac{2x_1 y_1 (x_{2n-1} + x_{2n-3})}{4} + \frac{(x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)(y_{2n-1} + y_{2n-3})}{4} \right) -$$

$$- \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_{2n-5} + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_{2n-5}}{4}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1) \left(\frac{2x_1 y_1 x_{2n-1} + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_{2n-1}}{4} + \right.$$

$$\left. + \frac{2x_1 y_1 x_{2n-3} + (x_1^2 + Dy_1^2)y_{2n-3}}{4} \right) - y_{2n-3}$$

$$= (x_1^2 + 1)(y_{2n+1} + y_{2n-1}) - y_{2n-3},$$

completing the proof.

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